

'Educational module 'foresters, it's your turn to play''

Introduction

Consultation between the various players in the five areas that have signed a Forestry Territory Charter (CFT) in Normandy has highlighted the need for coordinated action between players, as well as the need to explain what is being done in the forest. The aim of EUROFORNORM was therefore to create and run a regional network of forest areas in Normandy. "The future of Normandy's forests in the face of climate change" emerged as one of the priority themes.

Presentation of the educational game

"Forestiers, à vous de jouer" is an educational tool, in the form of a game, specifically on the theme of climate change in forests. It is aimed principally for primary school classes (cycle 3), with a number of players ranging from two to six. The aim is to manage the Normandy forest in the best possible way to protect it from the impacts of climate change. "Forestiers, à vous de jouer" is a board game in which the players have to reach the "Arrival" square by choosing the path of their choice and answering questions on 10 forestry themes. To promote this innovative tool, a copy of the module was given to 200 schools in the 5 departments of Normandy. This tool was designed with the aim of developing an educational resource that could complement other initiatives in the region, such as the "1000 communes, la forêt fait école" programme, developed by the National Federation of Forest Communities, which aims to entrust primary school children with the management of a plot of communal forest in order to raise their awareness of the forest as a central element of their region.

Lessons learned

One of the aims of creating this educational module for schools in the form of a game was to raise young people's awareness of forest management and the changes that can be expected in the face of climate change. Feedback from teachers who have used the game has been very positive, both in terms of the fun aspect of the game, which captures the attention of pupils, and in terms of the rich content of the topics covered. Teachers can integrate the various concepts into their own curriculum. In this way, pupils can learn about forest management and how Normandy's forests are adapting to climate change.

Figure 1. Presentation of the “Forestiers à vous de jouer” educational game box, game board and game cards.

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Further information

https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/euro-fornorm-14-50-61-emergence-and-animation-innovative-and-operational-network-normandy_en

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